

№5
27.08.2023

RESEARCH AND IMPLEMENTATION
TADQIQ VA TATBIQ
ILMIY-USLUBIY JURNALI

CERTIFICATE
№ 078777

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Jurnal oyda bir
marta nashr etiladi.

Nashr tillari:

O'zbek, rus, ingliz va
qoraqalpoq

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Prezidenti Administratsiyasi
huzuridagi
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2023-yil 3-mayda
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ARALASH TIPDAGI TENGLAMA UCHUN BITTA SILJISHLI MASALA YECHIMINING YAGONALIGI HAQIDA

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada aralash parabolik tenglama uchun integral shartli masala va uning yechimi yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: parabolik tenglama, aralash parabolik tenglama, differensial tenglama, funksiya, soha, integral tenglama.

ON THE HOMOGENEOUSITY OF SOLUTION TO A SINGLE-SHIFT PROBLEM FOR AN EQUATION OF MIXED TYPE

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Abstract: The article discusses an integral conditional problem and its solution for a mixed parabolic equation.

Key words: parabolic equation, mixed parabolic equation, differential equation, function, domain of definition, integral equation

Faraz qilaylik, $\Omega - y > 0$ bo'lganda uchlari $A(0,0)$, $B(1,0)$ nuqtalarda bo'lgan σ Jordan chizig'i bilan va $y < 0$ bo'lganda esa

$$AC: \xi = x - \frac{2}{m+2}(-y)^{\frac{m+2}{2}} = 0 \quad \text{va} \quad BC: \eta = x + \frac{2}{m+2}(-y)^{\frac{m+2}{2}} = 1$$

chiziqlar bilan chegaralangan soha bo'lsin.

Ω sohaning elliptik va giperbolik qismlarini mos ravishda Ω_1 va Ω_2 bilan belgilaymiz.

Quyidagi

$$\text{sign}y|y|^m u_{xx} + u_{yy} = 0, \quad m > 0 \quad (1)$$

aralash tipdagi tenglamani Ω sohada ko'ramiz.

Masala. Ω sohada (1) tenglamani quyidagi shartlarini qanoatlantiruvchi $U(x, y) \in C(\bar{\Omega}) \cap C^1(\Omega) \cap C^2(\Omega \setminus I)$ echimi topilsin:

$$U(x, y)|_{\sigma} = \varphi(x, y), \quad \forall x, y \in \sigma; \quad (2)$$

$$D_{0x}^{\alpha} [U(\theta(x))] = D_{0x}^{\alpha+\beta-1} x^{-\beta} U_y(x,0) + b(x), \quad (x,0) \in AB, \quad (3)$$

bu erda $\varphi(x, y)$, $b(x)$ -berilgan funksiyalar, $\alpha \in R$, $\beta = \frac{m}{2(m+2)}$, $\theta(x)$ -

(1) tenglamaning $(x,0) \in AB$ nuqtadan chiquvchi xarakteristikasi bilan AC xarakteristikaning kesishish nuqtalari; D_{0x}^{α} –Riman-Liuwill manosidagi kasr tartibli integrodifferensial operator [1].

Ekstremum prinsipi. Agar $b(x) \equiv 0$, $0 < \alpha < \beta$ bo'lsa, u holda masalaning $U(x, y)$ echimi $\bar{\Omega}_1$ yopig'ida o'zining musbat maksimum va manfiy minimum qiymatlariga σ chiziqda erishadi.

Isbot. (1) tenglamaning

$$\tau(x) = \lim_{y \rightarrow 0} U(x, y), \quad \nu(x) = \lim_{y \rightarrow 0} U_y(x, y)$$

shartlarini qanoatlantiruvchi Koshi masalasi echimi quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi [1].

$$U(\xi, \eta) = \gamma_1 \int_{\xi}^{\eta} \frac{(\eta - \xi)^{1-2\beta} \tau(t) dt}{(\eta - t)^{1-\beta} (t - \xi)^{1-\beta}} - \gamma_2 \int_{\xi}^{\eta} \frac{\nu(t) dt}{(\eta - t)^{\beta} (t - \xi)^{\beta}}, \quad (4)$$

$$\text{bu erda } \gamma_1 = \frac{\Gamma(2\beta)}{\Gamma^2(\beta)}, \quad \gamma_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{4}{m+2} \right)^{2\beta} \frac{\Gamma(1-2\beta)}{\Gamma^2(1-\beta)}.$$

(4) formuladan,

$$U(\theta(x)) = \gamma_1 \Gamma(\beta) x^{1-2\beta} D_{0x}^{-\beta} x^{\beta-1} \tau(x) - \gamma_2 \Gamma(1-\beta) D_{0x}^{\beta-1} x^{-\beta} \nu(x) \quad (5)$$

tenglikni olamiz.

(5) ifodani (3) chegaraviy shartga qo'yib,

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_1 \Gamma(\beta) D_{0x}^{\alpha} x^{1-2\beta} D_{0x}^{-\beta} x^{\beta-1} \tau(x) - \gamma_2 \Gamma(1-\beta) D_{0x}^{\alpha} D_{0x}^{\beta-1} x^{-\beta} \nu(x) = \\ = D_{0x}^{\alpha+\beta-1} x^{-\beta} U_y(x;0) + b(x) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

ifodani hosil qilamiz.

Ko'rsatish mumkinki,

$$D_{0x}^{\alpha} x^{1-2\beta} D_{0x}^{-\beta} x^{\beta-1} \tau(x) = x^{1-2\beta} F_{0x} \left[\begin{matrix} -\alpha, 2\beta-1 \\ \beta-\alpha, x \end{matrix} \right] x^{\beta-1} \tau(x) \quad (7)$$

bu erda $F_{0x} \left[\begin{matrix} a, b \\ c, x \end{matrix} \right]$ –umumlashgan kasr tartibli integro-differensial operator [2].

Haqiqatan ham,

$$D_{0x}^{\alpha} x^{1-2\beta} D_{0x}^{-\beta} x^{\beta-1} \tau(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(-\alpha)} \cdot \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_0^x (x-y)^{-\alpha-1} y^{1-2\beta} dy \int_0^y (y-z)^{\beta-1} z^{\beta-1} \tau(z) dz =$$

$$= \frac{1}{\Gamma(-\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_0^x z^{\beta-1} \tau(z) dz \int_z^x (x-y)^{-\alpha-1} y^{1-2\beta} (y-z)^{\beta-1} dy.$$

Ichki integralda $y = z + (x-z)s$ almashtirish bajarib, gipergeometrik funksiyaning integral ko‘rinishi

$$F(a, b, c; x) = \frac{\Gamma(c)}{\Gamma(b)\Gamma(c-b)} \int_0^1 t^{b-1} (1-t)^{c-b-1} (1-xt)^{-a} dt$$

formulasidan foydalansak,

$$\begin{aligned} D_{0x}^\alpha x^{1-2\beta} D_{0x}^{-\beta} x^{\beta-1} \tau(x) &= \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta-\alpha)} \int_0^x z^{-\beta} (x-z)^{-\alpha+\beta-1} F\left(\beta, 2\beta-1, -\alpha+\beta; \frac{z-x}{z}\right) \tau(z) dz = \\ &= \frac{x^{1-2\beta}}{\Gamma(\beta-\alpha)} \int_0^x z^{\beta-1} (x-z)^{-\alpha+\beta-1} F\left(\beta, 2\beta-1, -\alpha+\beta; \frac{x-z}{x}\right) \tau(z) dz. \end{aligned}$$

tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz. Bundan esa (7) tenglik to‘g‘ri ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

Agar (7) va

$$D_{0x}^\alpha D_{0x}^{\beta-1} x^{-\beta} v(x) = D_{0x}^{\alpha+\beta-1} x^{-\beta} v(x) \quad (8)$$

tengliklarni e‘tiborga olsak, (6) dan

$$(1 + \gamma_2 \Gamma(1-\beta)) D_{0x}^{\beta+\alpha-1} x^{-\beta} v(x) = \gamma_1 \Gamma(\beta) x^{1-2\beta} F_{0x} \left[\begin{matrix} -\alpha, 2\beta-1 \\ \beta-\alpha, x \end{matrix} \right] x^{\beta-1} \tau(x) \quad (9)$$

tenglik kelib chiqadi. Hosil bo‘lgan tenglikning har ikki tomoniga $D_{0x}^{1-\alpha-\beta}$ – differensial operatorni qo‘llaymiz.

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_1 \Gamma(\beta) D_{0x}^{-\alpha-\beta+1} x^{1-2\beta} F_{0x} \left[\begin{matrix} -\alpha, 2\beta-1 \\ \beta-\alpha; x \end{matrix} \right] x^{\beta-1} \tau(x) - \gamma_2 \Gamma(1-\beta) x^{-\beta} v(x) &= \\ &= x^{-\beta} U_y(x, 0) + D_{0x}^{-\alpha-\beta+1} b(x). \end{aligned}$$

U holda

$$(1 + \gamma_2 \Gamma(1-\beta)) x^{-\beta} v(x) = \gamma_1 \Gamma(\beta) x^{-\beta} D_{0x}^{1-2\beta} x^{\beta-1} \tau(x). \quad (10)$$

tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz.

$u(x, y)$ funksiya o‘zining ekstremal qiymatlariga Ω_1 sohada erishmaydi. Faraz qilaylik, $u(x, y)$ funksiya o‘zining musbat maksimum (manfiy minimum) qiymatiga $(x, 0) \in AB$ nuqtada erishsin. U holda, kasr tartibli differensial operatorlar uchun ekstremum prinsipiga [1] asosan musbat maksimum nuqta-sida $D_{0x}^{1-2\beta} x^{\beta-1} \tau(x) > 0$ (manfiy minimum nuqtasida esa $D_{0x}^{1-2\beta} x^{\beta-1} \tau(x) < 0$) ekanligidan musbat maksimum nuqtasida $v(x) > 0$ (manfiy minimum nuqtasida $v(x) < 0$) kelib chiqadi [1]. Oxirgi natija esa Zarembo-Jiro prinsipiga qarama-

qarshi bo‘ladi [3]. Demak, ekstremum prinsipining xulosasi to‘g‘ri. Bundan esa qo‘yilgan masala echimlari yagonaligi kelib chiqadi.

Adabiyotlar

1. Nasriddinov, O., Maniyozov, O., & Bozorqulov, A. (2023). Xususiy hosilali differensial tenglamalarning umumiy yechimni topishning xarakteristikalar usuli. *Research and implementation*.
2. Maniyozov, O., Shokirov, A., & Islomov, M. (2023). Matritsalarini arxitektura va dizayn sohasida tatbiqi. *Research and Implementation*. извлечено от <https://fer-teach.uz/index.php/rai/article/view/1007>.
3. Jo‘raeva, D. (2022). Buziladigan oddiy differensial tenglama uchun birinchi chegaraviy masala. *O‘zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali*, 2(13), 456-461.
4. To‘xtasinov, D. F. (2018). Didactic Bases Of Development Of Logical Thinking In Schoolchildren. *Central Asian Journal of Education*, 2(1), 68-74.
5. Nasriddinov, O., & Isomiddinova, O. (2023). Biologiya fanida differensial tenglamaga keluvchi masalani maple dasturida yechish. *Research and implementation*.
6. Ergashev, T. G., & Tulakova, Z. R. (2021). The Dirichlet problem for an elliptic equation with several singular coefficients in an infinite domain. *Russian Mathematics*, 65(7), 71-80.
7. Tolipov, N., Isaxonov, X., & Zunnunov, M. (2023). Shar tashqarisidagi soha uchun garmonik davom ettirish masalasi. *Research and implementation*.
8. Далиев, Б. С. (2021). Оптимальный алгоритм решения линейных обобщенных интегральных уравнений Абеля. *Проблемы вычислительной и прикладной математики*, 5(35), 120-129.
9. Madibragimova, I. M. (2023). Matematika darslarida muammoli ta’lim. *Principal issues of scientific research and modern education*, 2(6).
10. Yusupov, Y. A. (2018). Algorithms for adaptive identification of parameters of stochastic control objects. *Chemical Technology, Control and Management*, 2018(2), 74-77
11. Saidov, M., & Isroilov, S. (2023). To‘rtinchi tartibli bir jinsli bo‘lmagan tenglama uchun aralash masala. *Research and implementation*.
12. Isaqovich, T. N. (2023). Chorak doira tashqarisida bigarmonik tenglama uchun nokorrekt qo‘yilgan masala. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar ilmiy-uslubiy jurnali*, 1(18), 73-83.
13. Bozarov B.I. Optimal quadrature formulas with the trigonometric weight in the Sobolev space // Bulletin of the Institute of Mathematics, V.I. Romanovskiy Institute of Mathematics. – Tashkent, 2020. no 4. pp.1-10.

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